

A STUDY ON LACK OF INTEREST AND THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF SCHEDULED CASTE HIGHER SECONDARY STUDENTS

A. Xavier Joseph* & Dr. R. Arumugarajan**

* Research Scholar, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

** Principal, Bharat Institute of Education, Elathur, Tenkasi, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

This study aims at finding out attempts to find out whether the factor 'lack of interest' affects the socio-economic development of scheduled caste higher secondary students. Survey method was adopted for the study. Simple random sampling technique was used for collecting a sample of 715 higher secondary students from 79 schools in Kanyakumari district of Tamil Nadu State, India. The applied statistical techniques percentage analysis, 't' test, ANOVA, Pearson's product moment correlation, regression analysis and factor analysis revealed the following results. The level of lack of interest of majority of the SC higher secondary students was found to be moderate. A significant difference was found between male and female SC higher secondary students in their lack of interest and the female SC higher secondary students are better than the male SC higher secondary students in their lack of interest. A significant difference among government, aided and private school SC higher secondary students was found in their lack of interest and the private school SC higher secondary students are better in their lack of interest than the aided school and government school SC higher secondary students. A significant relationship was found between lack of interest and socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students. A significant influence of lack of interest on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students was found. The factor analysis of the correlation matrix for lack of interest on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students shows the presence of lack of interest with considerable factor loading.

Key Words: Lack of Interest, Socio-Economic Status, Higher Secondary Students & Scheduled Caste Students

Introduction:

"The social and economic deprivation among Scheduled Castes had been most common during pre and post-Independence. Therefore, there was a need of number of special safeguard policies. One of that is, 'Reservation Policy' in the Government Recruitment. The objective of the reservation policy is to eradicate the social and economic disparities which existed in the society" (Jadhav, 2008). In removing the socio-economic disparities, education plays an important role. The spread of education among the weaker sections of our society is vital as education is a prime requisite for socio-economic development (Rajeswari & Usha, 2014). Caste system has survived in India more than 3,500 years (Raj & Mani, 2014) and it could not be done away with till the present days. The interest to develop is a matter of personal attention and lack of interest is detrimental to the growth of an individual. Unless the individual desires to uplift himself from the pitfalls and oppressions of all forms, it may be rather difficult to rise up and move upward. Hence, this study attempts to find out the level of lack of interest of SC higher secondary students; and the relationship with and influence of lack of interest on the socio-economic status, since the results would be throwing flash of ray to improve the SC community students.

Significance of the Study:

Education is an in-born power and potentialities of individuals in the society and the acquisition of skills, aptitudes and competencies necessary for self-realization and coping with life problems (Achuonye & Ajoku, 2003). School education decides the future educational track of an individual. Higher secondary education is a life-turning point. Upon completion of this course, the students enter into specialized stream of education. So much of preparation and effort is made by the students to do well in the examinations at this point. In India caste system is followed and reservation is given education and employment to develop them. Various welfare schemes have been implemented to improve the SC community and yet they must willingly cooperate to make use of those opportunities to improve them socially and economically, and this requires enthusiasm and interest from the part of the SC students, without which they may not come up. Though we admit that "The Indian society is based on a caste system with vast inequalities in social, political, economic and educational spheres" (Barman, 2014), using the welfare schemes with interest they could come up in life, if they show interest. Kanniga and Karnan (2017) realizing the value say "socio economic status of the students is a very important aspect in the teaching learning process and is a major factor which influences the level of Achievement of the students in the modern society". It is in this context, this research is carried out to find out whether lack of interest affects the socio-economic development of scheduled caste higher secondary students. As no such study has been done so far, these findings of the study would be of social value. Hence this study becomes significant.

Objectives:

- ✓ To find out the level of lack of interest of higher secondary students
- ✓ To find out the level of lack of interest of higher secondary students with regard to gender
- ✓ To find out the level of lack of interest of higher secondary students with regard type of school
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference between male and female higher secondary students in their lack of interest
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant difference among government, aided and private higher secondary students in their lack of interest
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant relationship between lack of interest and socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant influence of lack of interest on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.
- ✓ To find out whether there is any significant factor with positive loading of the variable lack of interest on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.

Hypotheses:

- ✓ There is no significant difference between male and female SC higher secondary students in their lack of interest.
- ✓ There is no significant difference among government, aided and private SC higher secondary students in their lack of interest.
- ✓ There is no significant relationship between lack of interest and socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students
- ✓ There is no significant influence of lack of interest on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.
- ✓ There is no significant factor with positive loading of the variable lack of interest on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.

Methodology:

The investigator used survey method of research in this study. “Survey refers to the method of securing information concerning a phenomena under study from all or a selected number of respondents of the concerned universe” (Kothari, 2004). Simple random sampling was used to choose the sample from the population. A total sample of 715 higher secondary students, studying in higher secondary schools, was selected for the study. Among the 715 samples, 219 were drawn from Kuzhithurai, 244 were from Thuckalay and 252 were from Nagercoil educational districts of Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu, India. The investigator used 2 tools in the present study: (1) An inventory constructed and standardized by the investigator to identify the factor lack of interest of SC higher secondary students, and (2) The adapted tool of the Revised Socio Economic Status Scale for Urban and Rural India, by Kuppaswamy (2015). The statistical analysis Percentage analysis, differential analysis, correlation analysis, regression analysis and factor analysis were used for analyzing the data.

Analysis of Data:

Percentage Analysis:

Objective 1: To find out the level of lack of interest of SC higher secondary students.

Table 1: Level of Lack of Interest of SC Higher Secondary Students

Variable	Low		Moderate		High	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Lack of Interest	164	22.9	373	52.2	178	24.9

It is inferred from the above table that 22.9% of SC higher secondary students have low, 52.2% of them have moderate and 24.9% of them have high level of lack of interest. This has been shown in the Figure 1.

Objective 2: To find out the level of lack of interest of SC higher secondary students with respect to gender.

Table 2: Level of Lack of Interest of SC Higher Secondary Students with Respect to Gender

Variable	Gender	Low		Moderate		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Lack of interest	Male	106	28.0	193	50.9	80	21.1
	Female	58	17.3	180	53.5	98	29.2

It is inferred from the above table that 28.0% of male SC higher secondary students have low, 50.9% of them have moderate and 21.1% of them have high level of lack of interest. Regarding the female SC higher secondary students, 17.3% of them have low, 53.5% of them have moderate and 29.2% of them have high level of lack of interest. This has been shown in the Figure 2.

Objective 3: To find out the level of lack of interest SC higher secondary students with respect to type of school.

Table 3: Level of Lack of Interest of SC Higher Secondary Students with Respect to Type of School

Variable	Type of the School	Low		Moderate		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Lack of Interest	Government	83	25.9	165	51.6	72	22.5
	Aided	71	22.5	165	52.2	80	25.3
	Private	10	12.7	43	54.4	26	32.9

It is inferred from the above table that 25.9% of government school SC higher secondary students have low, 51.6% of them have moderate and 22.5% of them have high level of lack of interest. Regarding the aided school SC higher secondary students, 22.5% of them have low, 52.2% of them have moderate and 25.3% of them have high level of lack of interest. Regarding the private school SC higher secondary students, 12.7% of them have low, 54.4% of them have moderate and 32.9% of them have high level of lack of interest. This has been shown in the Figure 3.

Differential Analysis:

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between male and female SC higher secondary students in their lack of interest.

Table 4: Difference between Male and Female SC Higher Secondary Students in their Lack of Interest

Variable	Gender	N	Mean	S.D	Calculated 't' value	Remark
Lack of interest	Male	379	27.95	5.165	3.93	S
	Female	336	29.38	4.461		

(The table value of 't' is 1.96, S - Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 't' value (3.93) is greater than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, the result shows that there is significant difference between male and female SC higher secondary students in their lack of interest.

While comparing the mean scores of male (Mean=27.95) and female SC higher secondary students (Mean=29.38), the female SC higher secondary students are better than the male SC higher secondary students in their lack of interest. This has been shown in the Figure 4.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference among government, aided and private school SC higher secondary students in their lack of interest.

Table 5: Difference among Government, Aided and Private School SC Higher Secondary Students in their Lack of Interest

Variable	Source of variation	df (2, 712)		Calculated 'F' value	Remark
		Sum of squares	Mean square		
Lack of interest	Between	421.921	223.970	9.40	S
	Within	16473.856	21.418		

(For (2, 712) df the table value of 'F' is 3.00, S - Significant)

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 'F' value (9.40) is greater than the table value (3.00) for the df 2, 712 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the respective null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, the result shows that there is significant difference among government, aided and private school SC higher secondary students in their lack of interest. Scheffe test is used as post hoc test to find which of the paired mean scores differ significantly.

Table 5 (a): Scheffe Test Showing the Mean Difference in Lack of Interest with Respect to Type of School

Type of the School	N	Subset for alpha = 0.05	
		1	2
Government	320	28.18	
Aided	316	28.63	
Private	79		30.41

The Scheffe post hoc test result from the above table indicates that the private school SC higher secondary students are better in their lack of interest than the aided school and government school SC higher secondary students. This has been shown in the Figure 5.

Correlational Analysis:

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between lack of interest and socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.

Table 6: Relationship between Lack of Interest and Socio-Economic Status of SC Higher Secondary Students

Variables	N	df	Table 'γ' value	Calculated 'γ' value	Remarks
Lack of Interest and Socio-Economic Status	716	714	0.063	0.152	S

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated 'γ' value (0.152) is greater than the table value (0.063) for the df 714 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence there is significant relationship between lack of interest and socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students and the respective null hypothesis is rejected.

Regression Analysis:

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant influence of lack of interest on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.

Table 7 (a): Regression Analysis: Socio-Economic Status

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.288 ^a	.083	.074	3.933

The above regression table summarizes the model performance with relevant analysis. R represents the multiple correlation coefficient with a range lies between -1 and +1. Since the R value is 0.288, it means socio-economic status percentage has a positive relationship with poverty of SC higher secondary students.

R square represents the coefficient of determination and ranges between 0 and 1. Since the R square value is 0.083, 8% of the variation in socio-economic status is enhanced poverty of SC higher secondary students.

Table 7 (b): ANOVA – Socio-Economic Status

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	987.436	7	141.062	9.119	.000 ^b
	Residual	10936.620	707	15.469		
	Total	11924.056	714			

a. Dependent Variable: Socio-Economic Status

b. Predictors: (Constant), Lack of interest

From the above ANOVA table 'F' value is significant (significant value is less than 0.05) it means dependent variable socio-economic status is more reliable.

Table 7 (c): Regression Model - Coefficients

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	't' Value	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	β		
1	(Constant)	6.960	1.160		5.999	.000
	Lack of Interest	.105	.040	.126	2.621	.009

a. Dependent Variable: Socio-Economic Status

The above regression model coefficient table reports the coefficients for lack of interest helps to improve Socio-Economic Status significantly. The model coefficients are used in the construction of regression equation. The regression equation for the

Above data is: Socio-Economic Status percentage = 6.960 (constant) + 0.105 (lack of interest). From the regression equation, it is observed that lack of interest has a positive influence on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.

Factor Analysis:

Hypothesis 5: There is no significant factor with positive loading of the variable lack of interest on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.

Table 12: Factor Loading of Poverty on Socio-Economic Status of SC higher secondary students

Variable	Factor Loading	Nature of Variables
Lack of Interest	.665	Considerable presence

The factor analysis of the correlation matrix for poverty on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students shows the presence of poverty with considerable factor loading (.665).

Major Findings and Conclusion:

- ✓ The level of lack of interest of majority of the SC higher secondary students was found to be moderate.
- ✓ There is significant difference between male and female SC higher secondary students in their lack of interest and the female SC higher secondary students are better than the male SC higher secondary students in their lack of interest.
- ✓ There is significant difference among government, aided and private school SC higher secondary students in their lack of interest and the private school SC higher secondary students are better in their lack of interest than the aided school and government school SC higher secondary students.
- ✓ There is significant relationship between lack of interest and socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.
- ✓ There is significant influence of lack of interest on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students.
- ✓ The factor analysis of the correlation matrix for lack of interest on socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students shows the presence of lack of interest with considerable factor loading.

Therefore, on the whole, it could be concluded that lack of interest is one of the factors that affect the socio-economic status of SC higher secondary students. However, it could be further confirmed as the study is limited to the geographical location of Kanyakumari district in Tamil Nadu State alone.

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